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SPHERE RECONSTITUTION BY THE
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ABSTRACT

The Sphere Reconstitution or "global solution" combines the intermediate quantities (abscissae) derived from HIPPARCOS data, to obtain the five astrometric parameters for all virtually single stars (perhaps 85-90,000 out of the 100,000 programme stars). The solution allows one abscissa zero-point correction per Reference Great Circle and a few tens of "global parameters" representing large-scale distortions of the system of positions *e.g.* from thermal/instrumental effects and optical chromaticity. However, terms for the gravitational light deflection in a generalized metric for the Solar System may also be included.

1. INTRODUCTION

A previous paper (Lindegren and Petersen, 1985) described the production of one abscissa per object observed in a "set" of 6 to 12 hours, by means of the Great Circle Reductions or set solutions. In this process, the abscissa origin of each set was chosen quite arbitrarily, since it was not possible to relate the observations uniquely to a specific positional reference system. The purpose of the Sphere Reconstitution or *global solution* is, firstly, to relate all the different sets to a single, common reference system by determining a consistent array of set zero-point corrections $\{a_j\}$ and, secondly, to determine the positions, proper motions, and parallaxes of all "single" stars in this system. (Stars suspected of duplicity and other problematic objects are temporarily thrown out of this process.)

In outline, the global solution does the following. The abscissae are treated one star at a time and the observation equations for the five astrometric parameters set up. The abscissae are examined for slit errors, which are removed if possible, and for signs of duplicity or other effects which would exclude the star from the global solution.

The astrometric parameters are preadjusted and, if the star shall contribute to the global solution, eliminated from the equations, which are then added to the normals for the zero-point corrections. When all stars have been processed in this way, we are left with a dense system of normal equations for the ~2000 zero-point corrections, which are solved and applied. The whole process is iterated until the corrections become negligible.

2. THE OBSERVATION EQUATION

Let $(\alpha_i, \delta_i, \Pi_i, \mu_{\alpha i}, \mu_{\delta i})$ be the astrometric parameters and ρ_i the radial velocity of star i , referring to the adopted mean epoch of the mission (T_0). The coordinate direction at the mid-time (T_j) of set number j is

$$\bar{u}_{ij} = \langle d_i + (\mu_i + d_i \rho_i \Pi_i / a_U)(T_j - T_0) - \mathbf{b}_E(T_j) \Pi_i / a_U \rangle \quad (1)$$

where $\langle \rangle$ is the vector normalization operator, a_U the astronomical unit, $\mathbf{b}_E$ the barycentric position of the Earth, and

$$d_i = N \begin{bmatrix} c\delta_i c\alpha_i \\ c\delta_i s\alpha_i \\ s\delta_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mu_i = N \begin{bmatrix} -\mu_{\alpha i} c\delta_i s\alpha_i - \mu_{\delta i} s\delta_i c\alpha_i \\ \mu_{\alpha i} c\delta_i c\alpha_i - \mu_{\delta i} s\delta_i s\alpha_i \\ \mu_{\delta i} c\delta_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (2a, b)$$

with N being the equatorial coordinate triad (Paper I). If, furthermore, the reference system of set j is given in equatorial coordinates by the three angles α_j, δ_j, c_j [Paper II, Eqn (1)], we have uniquely the "calculated" abscissa $a_{ij}^{(calc)}$ by means of Eqn (2) in Paper II.

Comparing this calculated value with the "observed" abscissa from the set solution, we have the observation equation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial \alpha_i} \Delta \alpha_i + \frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial \delta_i} \Delta \delta_i + \frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial \Pi_i} \Delta \Pi_i + \tau_j \frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial \alpha_i} \Delta \mu_{\alpha i} + \tau_j \frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial \delta_i} \Delta \mu_{\delta i} - \Delta c_j + \\ + \sum_m \frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial \Gamma_m} \Delta \Gamma_m + \text{noise} = a_{ij}^{(obs)} - a_{ij}^{(calc)} + ns \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with $\tau_j = T_j - T_0$. $\{\Gamma_m\}$ are the global parameters to be discussed in Section 4; n is a small integer to account for the slit errors and $s = 1/g_{10}$ (Paper II) is the mean slit period. For preliminary solutions based on only part of the mission (*e.g.* 6, 12, or 18 months of observation), it is foreseen to include only the first two or three astrometric parameters per star, and no global parameter.

3. LEAST-SQUARES SOLUTION

The solution method, involving pre-adjustment and elimination of the astrometric parameters, is exactly analogous to the method used for the set solution and described in Section 4 of Paper II. In the notations of that paper, $\Delta\Omega_k$ is the correction vector to the astrometric parameters of star $k = i$, while Δa is the vector of corrections to the set zero points and global parameters.

Having collected all abscissae pertaining to star i , the normalized observation equations (II.7) are set up and the sub-normals (II.8a) constructed and factored as in (II.9). After $\Delta\Omega$ has been solved (assuming $\Delta a = 0$) and the astrometric parameters adjusted, we investigate the residuals $e - B\Delta\Omega$, first with respect to slit errors. These will usually cause residuals of several tenths of an arcsec, that is many times the typical abscissa mean error (<0.01 arcsec), and are therefore easy to detect. To find the correct combination of integers n in the 60 or so observation equations like (3), a special algorithm called MESH is invoked.

The MESH algorithm modifies the right-hand side of the observation equations corresponding to a number of trial positions in a mesh around the current catalogue position (α_i, δ_i) . Let (A, D) be the offset angles in a certain mesh point. Then choose the integer n in each equation to make the residual with respect to the mesh point absolutely less than $\frac{1}{2}s$, namely

$$n = \text{NINT} \left[\left(a_{ij}^{(\text{obs})} - a_{ij}^{(\text{calc})} - \frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial \alpha_i} A - \frac{\partial a_{ij}}{\partial \delta_i} D \right) s^{-1} \right] \quad (4)$$

and solve the normals with the modified right-hand side. The process is repeated for different mesh points until acceptable residuals are obtained. This algorithm will always find the correct slit errors, provided that the search is made in a sufficient area and with a dense enough mesh ($\Delta A = \Delta D \lesssim 0.5$ arcsec; Andreasen, 1983). However, it may happen that the residuals look reasonable for more than one combination of slit errors, in which case there is no way to decide with certainty which solution is correct. The probability that this will happen is rather significant after only 6 or 12 months' observation, but is normally very small after the full $2\frac{1}{2}$ years.

At this point, it is decided whether the star will be used in the determination of the set zero points. Reasons for excluding the star may be: duplicity known or suspected from the Input Catalogue or IDT signal processing (location estimator); bad residuals even after the MESH procedure; ambiguous slit errors in MESH; the star is not in a predefined category (*e.g.*, it is required to make separate global solutions for different categories of stars in order to investigate systematic errors). If the star is accepted, the second part of the sub-normals (II.8b) is constructed and the modified equations (II.10) added to

the normal equations for the zero-point corrections and the global parameters.

The resulting system of equations, after all programme stars are thus processed, is quite dense and we will not use reordering to reduce the profile as in the set solutions. Element (j_1, j_2) in the coefficient matrix is non-zero if the two sets j_1, j_2 have at least one accepted (contributing) star in common. If 60,000 programme stars are used in the final solutions, this is true for almost every pair of sets. The upper-triangular part of the matrix is stored columnwise on disc, in blocks of a fixed size; any two of these blocks can be simultaneously in the primary memory of the computer. The normals are solved by the method of Cholesky with three or six set origins kept fixed (depending on whether proper motions are included) to eliminate the rank defect. [Actually it appears that the normals are *not* singular after accumulation, but have a condition number of the order of 10^4 only, which is not due to rounding errors. The equations can therefore very well be solved without fixing some origins. This somewhat unexpected feature is probably due to our postulating the positions of the RGC poles (α_j, δ_j) instead of treating them as unknowns, but the effect in the end seems to be negligible.] The unique "pseudo-solution" (minimum norm) is finally calculated by subtracting from the solution vector its projection into the null-space. The null-space is spanned by the (three or) six linearly independent vectors whose j th components are $N^i r_j$ and $N^i r_j \tau_j$. The orthogonalized null-vectors are conveniently stored in the last block of the normal equations, along with the right-hand side.

The least-squares adjustment will be iterated until the set zero-point corrections become negligible. Usually only the right-hand side of the normal equations is calculated afresh, while the Cholesky factorized matrix is unchanged. (The full observation equations must be recomputed, however, as they are not stored.) This only calls for a provision to ensure that exactly the same stars are included in the normals as in the previous iteration.

4. GLOBAL PARAMETERS

The global parameters $\{\Gamma_m\}$ are coefficients of proportionality for the systematic displacement of the abscissa as function of some known and variable condition. Three kinds of global parameters have been considered:

(i) Thermal-instrumental effects, in particular a periodic variation of the abscissa displacement with $a_{ij} - a_{sj}$, where a_{sj} is the abscissa of the Sun in set j . Such effects can be expected as a result of periodic variations of the basic angle. The Fourier coefficients of the displacement are regarded as global parameters.

(ii) "Constant chromaticity", *i.e.*, a displacement proportional to the colour index arising from that component of the instrument chromaticity which is independent of both field index and field coordinates and therefore indeterminable in the set solution [*cf.* Paper II, Eqn (4)]. Different values may be assumed for different parts of the mission, but it is probably necessary to assume constancy over considerable periods (≥ 6 months) to determine the effect.

(iii) Parameters expressing the gravitational light deflection in a generalized space-time metric for the Solar System according to a development by Cowling (1983). Apart from the deflection predicted by General Relativity (which amounts to several milliarcsec and is always included in the calculation of proper directions), this contains also axisymmetric and non-axisymmetric terms and terms depending on the inverse square of the distance from the Sun, all of which are expected to be very small if not zero.

Numerical simulations involving up to 10,000 stars and 500 sets (positions and parallaxes only) have been made with various combinations of global parameters of the type (i) and (iii). It turns out that all Fourier coefficients in (i) can be determined with high accuracy, *except* that of $\sin(a_{ij} - a_{sj})$, which is very strongly correlated with a general zero-point error of the parallaxes. Some of the Cowling parameters are also strongly correlated with each other and with some of the Fourier parameters, and it will in general be difficult to separate instrumental effects from hypothetical deviations from General Relativity. The potential accuracy of many of these global parameters is in the range of 5 - 10 microarcsec (Söderhjelm and Lindegren, 1985). Inclusion of these parameters is primarily intended as a method to diagnose subtle instrumental effects, which are otherwise likely to go unnoticed.

As a general rule, 10 to 20 global parameters (without large internal correlations) can be included in the solution with very little effect on the accuracy of the set zero points. The correlations between the zero points of different sets are typically a few per cent only, and the expected formal mean errors for the full-scale solution (2000 sets, 60,000 contributing stars) are about 0.1 milliarcsec. Interestingly, a $\pm 10\%$ modulation of the mean errors is observed, with the minimum occurring for sets with the RGC pole near the ecliptic and the maximum for those with the pole at latitude $\pm 43^\circ$.

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